

ARTICLE

Freshwater Ecology

Untangling the roles of centrality and environmental contribution in diversity patterns across spatial scales

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Abstract

The application of graph theory to metacommunity ecology allows a deeper analysis of the effect of network structure on diversity patterns. Here, we set out to test the role of network centrality metrics and environmental characteristics in diversity patterns of pond macroinvertebrate metacommunities. We tested two approaches to construct the networks: one used the percolation distance, whereas the other was based on a community-contingent distance. The role of each patch within the network was then analyzed using its centrality value. Later, we analyzed the relationships between the macroinvertebrate diversity and centrality metrics for four study sites. The calculated diversity metrics cover different facets of biodiversity at two scales: pond and pondscape. Environmental characteristics of the studied ponds were also included. All relationships were tested considering the entire macroinvertebrate dataset, but also differentiated by dispersal mode (i.e., active vs. passive) and considering the two types of network approaches analyzed. The results were mostly consistent when comparing the network approaches used. Centrality metrics tended to be positively related to alpha and negatively to beta diversity. Environmental uniqueness showed a positive effect on beta diversity metrics, regardless of the dispersal mode. We only observed a weak negative relationship between eutrophication and species richness of active dispersers. Pond size showed a positive effect on both alpha and beta diversity, but was detected more frequently on alpha diversity metrics. We could not find evidence for a clear negative effect of habitat degradation on diversity. We found a greater importance of environmental characteristics versus the centrality metrics for both alpha and beta diversity of active dispersers, while a combination of their contributions for passive dispersers. An unexpected importance of centrality was observed for alpha diversity of passive dispersers. Using empirical data, we demonstrate that the centrality of a patch in an undirected network affects diversity regardless of the approach used to construct the networks, with a higher influence at local scale regardless of the dispersal mode. This study broadens knowledge of the relationships

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between environmental features and network centrality, demonstrating the important role of centrality as a determinant of diversity in metacommunities.

KEYWORDS

connectivity, environmental characteristics, macroinvertebrates diversity, network, wetlands

INTRODUCTION

Metacommunity theory relates local scale patterns of species diversity to regional scale processes (O'Dwyer & Green, 2010) along a multidimensional continuum of community assembly dynamics (Cottenie, 2005; Leibold et al., 2004). Within this framework, dispersal is responsible for connecting processes happening at both regional and local scales, which can ultimately lead to a progressive homogenization of a metacommunity (Chase, 2003; Mouquet & Loreau, 2003). The proximity of localities within a region as well as other landscape attributes such as barriers can influence dispersal rates (e.g., Fournier et al., 2017; Germain et al., 2019). Therefore, the exchange of individuals by dispersal between communities inhabiting distinct patches of a network (i.e., a spatial network) is highly determined by the connections among them and is one of the main determinants of metacommunity functioning (Borthagaray et al., 2020; Hubbell, 2001; Leibold et al., 2004). Indeed, connectivity can limit the movement of genes, individuals, or populations among patches (Erős et al., 2012; Gonzalez et al., 2017), with effects at different spatial scales (Tischendorf & Fahrig, 2000). Hence, the position of a community within the landscape will ultimately determine its connectivity, which is crucial for local and regional community assembly processes (Borthagaray et al., 2023), and this explains the importance of patch or community isolation within the framework of spatial biological theory (Economato & Keitt, 2010).

However, quantifying connectivity for a certain patch within the network is still challenging. A popular way to measure connectivity is, for instance, assessing the structural connectivity by means of the geographical position of the different patches, using some kind of eigenanalysis, that is, Moran eigenvector maps (García-Girón et al., 2020; Marini et al., 2019) or principal coordinates of neighbor matrices analyses (Landeiro et al., 2011). But these methods have some inconveniences: (1) they do not consider the actual network, usually only including the sampled patches/communities (Arim et al., 2016); and (2) they disregard the fact that organisms have different landscape perceptions due to their different dispersal abilities (Gonzalez et al., 2017; Shanafelt et al., 2015). Therefore, there arises the need to include a more

functional connectivity measure that could link the geographical position with the organisms' landscape perception. To solve these issues, graph theory has been proposed as a robust and promising tool for the quantification of the spatial network structure and local community isolation (Borthagaray, Berazategui, et al., 2015). However, its application to metacommunity ecology is still under development (Almeida-Gomes et al., 2020; but see Cunillera-Montcusi et al., 2020, in a pond network). Indeed, graph theory allows us to obtain a spatial network considering (1) a more complete spatial coverage, including not only the sampled patches but also other patches, thus obtaining a patch centrality value for all patches that make up the network, and (2) the organisms' landscape perception. The centrality values obtained may reflect the potential flow of individuals through a local patch and therefore quantify their importance within the centrality gradient of the entire network (Borthagaray, Berazategui, et al., 2015; Estrada & Bodin, 2008). Thus, larger values of centrality indicate lower levels of patch isolation (Economato & Keitt, 2010). In this sense, several network centrality metrics are used because they inform about the gradient of patch centrality within a network at different scales, from the local neighborhood to the global network (Dale, 2017; Economato & Keitt, 2010; Estrada & Bodin, 2008). "Degree," "betweenness," and "closeness" centrality metrics are effective for measuring spatial connectivity because each formulation of centrality captures a unique aspect, from a smaller to a larger scale connectivity, respectively (Dallas et al., 2020; Estrada & Bodin, 2008). Thus, "degree centrality" corresponds to the flux of dispersal directly entering a patch from neighboring patches, whereas "closeness centrality" measures the global position of a patch in a network because it represents how close the patch is to all other patches. "Betweenness centrality" highlights the role of a patch connecting all other patches in the network and thus those acting as stepping stones (Borthagaray, Pinelli, et al., 2015; Dallas et al., 2020). However, some caution is needed when using them because they are sensitive to the linkage distance used to construct the network. For example, the network could be obtained using only the geographical position of the patches (e.g., using either a percolation distance or the minimum spanning tree;

Rozenfeld et al., 2008; Urban & Keitt, 2001). Consequently, the resulting network might not necessarily reflect the organisms' landscape perception. Nevertheless, the network could also be constructed using a distance more closely related to organisms' landscape perception (Calabrese & Fagan, 2004). Following this rationale, Borthagaray, Berazategui, et al. (2015) introduced a new methodology using graph theory to define a taxon-contingent network, which empirically detects the scale at which some ecological processes such as dispersion operate. We will use it here to test which kind of network better reflects diversity patterns at different scales. In this sense, we expect an overall better fit for diversity patterns, with the centrality metrics obtained using a community-contingent network approach (Hypothesis 1, hereafter H1, Figure 1).

Increasing connectivity across the landscape would homogenize species composition among patches reducing communities' dissimilarity and thus decreasing beta diversity (Chase, 2003; Jamoneau et al., 2018; Mouquet & Loreau, 2003). At the same time, connectivity would facilitate species arrivals in more central patches, thereby increasing alpha diversity (Altermatt et al., 2013; Economo & Keitt, 2010). Therefore, we expect a negative relationship between patch centrality and beta diversity, but a positive relationship between patch centrality and alpha diversity (Hypothesis 2, hereafter H2, Figure 1). Besides, we also expect that network centrality metrics that better capture larger network dynamics—closeness or betweenness—would largely explain the patterns of beta diversity, and the one which better captures smaller network dynamics—degree—would rather explain alpha diversity patterns (Hypothesis 3, hereafter H3, Figure 1).

In addition to connectivity, other drivers must be considered when analyzing diversity patterns. Indeed, previous studies suggest that diversity values are more linked to environmental variability than to connectivity (Hodgson et al., 2011) at both local and regional scales (Gianuca et al., 2017; Heino & Tolonen, 2017a; Hill et al., 2019). Therefore, when analyzing diversity patterns, patch environmental characteristics must not be overlooked. Including the environmental uniqueness of patches will give an idea of patch environmental heterogeneity within the network that can influence both the alpha and beta diversity patterns. According to the literature (Legendre, 2014; Vilmi et al., 2017), sites with a low number of species are usually those with greater ecological uniqueness or extreme ecological conditions. Moreover, an increase in the environmental heterogeneity implies an increase in the variety of environmental conditions to which different species are adapted (Heino et al., 2015; Maloufi et al., 2016). Thus, we expect a negative alpha diversity–environmental uniqueness

relationship and a positive beta diversity–environmental uniqueness relationship (hypothesis 4, hereafter H4, Figure 1). The eutrophic state of the patch is also important because it could act as a filter for some species (Stendera et al., 2012), lowering alpha diversity values or homogenizing the species composition across patches, and so decreasing beta diversity. However, because nutrient-rich environments tend to present more stochastic community assemblages, a positive beta diversity trend can also be observed (Chase, 2010). Thus, we expect a negative effect of the trophic state on alpha diversity, but no clear trend when analyzing beta diversity (Hypothesis 5, hereafter H5, Figure 1). Aside from these environmental characteristics, others might also be relevant, like the patch size. According to the power law, larger patches (i.e., bigger ponds) might host a higher number of species mainly because they might provide larger targets for species to colonize and a greater variety of habitats allowing species to coexist (Arrhenius, 1921; MacArthur & Wilson, 1967). Consequently, we expect higher alpha and beta diversity values in larger patches (Hypothesis 6, hereafter H6, Figure 1). Finally, we also include the habitat condition to assess the degree of habitat degradation in each patch. Habitat degradation can lead to a functional homogenization process (Abadie et al., 2011; Gascón et al., 2012) due to the loss of more specialist species (Lockwood & McKinney, 2001). Thus, we expect a negative effect of habitat degradation for both alpha diversity (because of species loss) and beta diversity (because the remaining species will be the most tolerant species within the regional species pool, thus decreasing beta diversity) (Hypothesis 7, hereafter H7, see Figure 1).

Finally, the dispersal ability of organisms might also influence diversity patterns, affecting both alpha and beta diversity values (Sarremejane et al., 2017), hence the need to analyze different modes of dispersal. In the present work, we used macroinvertebrate communities as our target assemblages. The latter constitute an ideal group to address metacommunity ecology (Florenco et al., 2014; Tornero et al., 2018), presenting different dispersal modes and abilities that allow them to move among interconnected patches; in most cases, this ability allows them to track local environmental changes effectively. For example, passive dispersers are expected to have a more stochastic dispersal and thus to be more affected by spatial structuring than active dispersers that might be more under environmental control (Grönroos et al., 2013; Heino, 2013). Thus, active and passive dispersers might respond differently to spatial and environmental variables, and these different responses might be translated to a different influence when looking at alpha and beta diversity patterns. Indeed, we expect that active and

FIGURE 1 Diagram showing the hypotheses considered in this study. H stands for hypothesis.

passive dispersers' diversity will be more strongly linked to environmental characteristics rather than to patch centrality value when analyzing alpha diversity patterns, whereas the effect of environmental characteristics on beta diversity patterns might be more noticeable for active dispersers due to their better ability of tracking environmental variability than that of passive dispersers (Hypothesis 8, hereafter H8, Figure 1).

Here, we examined how the spatial network centrality value of the patches is linked to alpha and beta diversity patterns in macroinvertebrate metacommunities, while also considering the potential role of environmental characteristics. We used pondscapes as model systems because they are excellent systems for studying the effect of spatial connectivity on diversity patterns; this is because (1) they are good examples of patchy habitats separated by a terrestrial matrix (Boothby, 1997); (2) they can cover a broad gradient of connectivity, that is, from isolated to highly connected ponds; and (3) the local and regional scales can be easily separated with the local scale referring to ponds and the regional scale referring to pondscapes (Boix et al., 2020; De Meester et al., 2005). We studied four sites (i.e., pondscapes), and in each one, we evaluated the centrality of patches (i.e., ponds) by calculating different metrics. We followed two approaches to construct the spatial networks. One network was built based on the percolation distance, whereas the other network was built using the community-contingent distance. Because the network structure has a major impact on community and metacommunity diversity patterns (Desjardins-Proulx & Gravel, 2012; Economo & Keitt, 2008, 2010), here we will analyze its potential effect on diversity by comparing the results of the two approaches (percolation vs. community-contingent). We worked with the entire communities' dataset, as well as splitting the data into active and passive dispersers. We also considered several diversity metrics to cover the different facets of biodiversity (species richness, species diversity, and phylogenetic diversity). We then investigated whether alpha diversity (calculated for each pond) and beta diversity (calculated as the contribution of each pond to the overall pondscape diversity) patterns are mainly explained by local environmental characteristics or network centrality metrics or by a combination of both.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study sites

We studied four different sites (i.e., pondscapes) (Figure 2). All sites are located in protected natural areas. One is located in the island of Sardinia (Italy), Giara di

Gesturi (hereafter Giara), and the other three are located in the Iberian Peninsula, Albera and Clots de Guils (hereafter Guils) in Spain, and Vila Nova de Milfontes (hereafter Vila Nova) in Portugal. Although they are located within the Mediterranean region, each site presents its own intrinsic characteristics because each is exposed to different local features (Ballón et al., 2016). Albera, Vila Nova, and Giara include lowland ponds, whereas Guils includes mountain ponds. Vila Nova is located at sea level and has Atlantic influence. Giara is located in a plateau. More information on these sites and their macroinvertebrate communities can be found in Tornero et al. (2018) for Vila Nova and Giara, Cunillera-Montcusí et al. (2019) for Albera, and Cunillera-Montcusí et al. (2020) for Guils.

Sampling and laboratory work

We sampled 10–12 temporary ponds of a wide range of sizes in each site (Appendix S1: Table S1). Each site was visited once coinciding with the middle phase of the hydroperiod to avoid periods involving drastic changes in the community structure (Boix et al., 2016). Hence, sampling from Albera, Guils, and Giara occurred from February 2012 to July 2012, and in the case of Vila Nova, sampling was carried out in April 2013. In Albera and Vila Nova, 12 ponds were sampled; in Guils and Giara, 10 and 11 ponds were sampled, respectively. In total, we studied the communities of macroinvertebrates in 45 temporary ponds within the Mediterranean region.

The macroinvertebrates were sampled using a dip net with a diameter of 22 cm and a mesh size of 250 μm . The sampling procedure was based on an effort of 20 dip net sweeps in rapid sequence that spanned all the different mesohabitats (Boix et al., 2005). The implemented sampling procedure attempted to solve two problems that we have to face when sampling ponds of different sizes. To solve this problem with the trade-off between “reliability” (the same effort in a big pond implies a lower proportion of sampled area) and “sampling effort standardization,” we sampled the ponds proportionally according to their size, and then, after homogenizing the capture, we standardized the effort. The procedure was as follows: in small ponds ($<5000 \text{ m}^2$), the sample was obtained by means of 20 dip net sweeps. In medium ponds ($5000\text{--}20,000 \text{ m}^2$), 40 dip net sweeps were conducted; then, the capture was homogenized, and only half of this (equivalent to 20 dip net sweeps) constituted the sample. Finally, in big ponds ($>20,000 \text{ m}^2$), 60 dip net sweeps were performed; the capture was then homogenized, and one third (equivalent to 20 dip net sweeps) of the total capture constituted the sample, with the rest being

FIGURE 2 Location map of the four studied sites (i.e., pondscape). For each site, darker and larger circles correspond to the sampled ponds (between 10 and 12 in each site) and other waterbodies that encompass the spatial network are smaller and shown in a lighter color. In this case, the percolation networks are shown. Each network is obtained by linking the pairs of patches that reach the minimum distance linking the whole patch system, that is, the percolation distance (PDist), which is expressed in meters.

released into the water. Samples were preserved in situ in ethanol 96%. Subsequently, in the laboratory, the fixative of the samples was removed, and individuals were sorted, counted, and identified to the species level when possible (using among others Di Sabatino et al., 2010; Franciscolo, 1979; Heidemann & Seidenbusch, 2002; Nieser et al., 1994; Langton, 1991; Smith, 1989).

Variables related to water characteristics, habitat condition, and pond size were also measured. Water characteristics were measured the same day macroinvertebrate sampling was done (Appendix S1: Table S2). Thus, water temperature, dissolved oxygen, conductivity, pH (model Hach HQ30d), and water column depth values were obtained in situ. Other parameters such as soluble reactive phosphate, dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN, calculated as the sum of the concentrations of ammonia, nitrite, and nitrate), total nutrients (total nitrogen and total phosphorus [TP]), dissolved organic carbon, total organic carbon, fulvic acid content, planktonic chlorophyll *a*, macrophyte biomass, the ratio between DIN and TP (molar DIN/molar TP), and absorbance at 440 nm were also determined following the procedures described in Ballón et al. (2016).

We also measured the habitat condition with a rapid assessment method (Estat de Conservació d'Ecosistemes Lenítics Soms [ECELS] index; Sala et al., 2004) as a proxy of habitat degradation. This index integrates information on five components to evaluate habitat condition: basin littoral morphology (Component 1), human activity (Component 2), water descriptors such as odor and transparency (Component 3), emergent vegetation (Component 4), and hydrophytic vegetation (Component 5). Values of this index range from 0 (worst habitat condition) to 100 (best habitat condition). Finally, pond size was estimated using the Google Maps Area Calculator Tool and then checked in the field.

Building the spatial network: Two approaches

The whole set of waterbodies configuring each site was determined from aerial photographs from Google Earth. To establish the total area for identifying waterbodies, we created a polygon linking the most external sampled

ponds and then constructed an outer polygon from the maximum distance between the two most distant sampled ponds as a buffer distance (see Appendix S1: Figure S1). This outer polygon gave us the total area to be scanned while looking for other waterbodies that finally conformed the network. From here onward, we refer to the area of that outer polygon as SEA, that is, spatial extent measured as an area (Heino et al., 2014), which was extracted from Google Earth Pro (see Appendix S1: Table S1 and Figure S2, to see the relationships with other common descriptors of network structure). Then, to build the network, we used two different approaches using graph

theory based on two different distances (i.e., percolation and community-contingent). See Figure 3 for the example of one site (i.e., Giara) on how different could become the networks obtained using each approach.

Percolation network

The percolation distance (PDist) is the minimum distance at which all waterbodies of the network are connected to at least one neighbor node (Rozenfeld et al., 2008; Solé, 2011; Urban & Keitt, 2001). This distance determines the

FIGURE 3 Resulting Giara network constructed using four different distances to connect the patches: (A) percolation network (PDist = 2265 m), (B) entire community-contingent network (entire community-contingent distance = 9782.5 m), (C) active dispersers' community-contingent network (active dispersers' community-contingent distance = 9733.5 m), and (D) passive dispersers' community-contingent network (passive dispersers' community-contingent distance = 6059 m). The sampled ponds are shown with larger circles and in dark orange, whereas the rest of the waterbodies comprising the network are in light orange.

transition from a fragmented to a connected landscape in which all waterbodies are virtually reachable, but their distribution through the landscape is still preserved. Several studies have reported that across a gradient of species dispersal and for different landscape structures, this percolation distance determines an abrupt transition in species' potential to move at the local or at the global level (Bertuzzo et al., 2016; Borthagaray et al., 2014; Cunillera-Montcusí et al., 2021; Urban & Keitt, 2001; With & Crist, 1995). We estimated the percolation network for each site (see Figure 2).

Community-contingent network

In order to build a network considering the potential dispersal distances of the organisms, we looked for the scale (i.e., the distance) at which diversity patterns are more congruent with landscape, assuming then that the main ecological processes (e.g., dispersal) are operating at that scale. Therefore, the obtained spatial connectivity network would suggest a maximum congruence between diversity and centrality metrics. To build the network, we followed the procedure detailed in Borthagaray, Berazategui, et al. (2015), but instead of focusing on different taxa as they did (and obtaining taxon-contingent networks), here we worked with the entire macroinvertebrate community dataset because we had communities with many taxa and the number of resulting taxon-contingent networks would be excessive. Briefly, the procedure is described as follows. (1) We constructed a set of networks, that is, we used a gradient of geographic distances calculating the number of break points dividing the maximum edge-to-edge Euclidean distance by the minimum edge-to-edge Euclidean distance between water bodies; this gradient reflects the wide range of potential dispersal distances (linkage distances) in a metacommunity pool; therefore, we had one network for each of the break points considered. (2) We calculated "eigenvector centrality" for each patch in the network at every linkage distance. Eigenvector centrality is an index that ranks communities not only by the number of direct connections but also by the number of connections that their neighbors have (Bonacich, 1972; Wasserman & Faust, 1994). (3) We calculated the correlation between "eigenvector centrality" and local species richness of the sampled ponds in each network. (4) Lastly, we identified the maximum significant correlation (absolute) value between them and kept that linkage distance and the corresponding network. This network maximizes the association between the patch centrality (i.e., pond) and local diversity for the community. If the distance for which the correlation is maximum generates a network without a minimum centrality gradient

among the sampled ponds (i.e., at least 40% of the values of centrality are different), then the distance selected is the one with the second highest correlation value, which ensures a gradient in the values of centrality among the sampled ponds.

Centrality metrics

Once the percolation and the community-contingent networks were obtained for each site, we calculated three metrics that focus on different concepts and definitions of centrality: "degree centrality," "betweenness centrality," and "closeness centrality" (Borthagaray, Pinelli, et al., 2015; Economo & Keitt, 2008). Degree centrality corresponds to the number of direct links between patches and is then dependent on the local centrality of that patch. Betweenness centrality quantifies how frequently a waterbody is located on the shortest path between every possible pair of other water bodies; that is, patches acting as stepping stones to the rest of the network. Closeness centrality is the average length of the shortest path between one waterbody and the rest, or, in other words, how close a patch is from all others; therefore, it measures the centrality of a patch within the whole network (Borthagaray, Pinelli, et al., 2015). These three metrics were calculated with R package "sna" (Butts, 2016; R Core Team, 2018). In the case of the community-contingent networks, if the distances used to construct them were below the percolation distance (i.e., we obtained disconnected graphs), we corrected closeness values for each network component. All the described procedure to construct the community-contingent network in order to calculate the centrality metrics was also repeated considering the dispersal mode of the organisms. Thus, the data were divided into two groups: active dispersers' community and passive dispersers' community based on Tachet et al. (2000) (see Appendix S1: Table S3).

Diversity metrics

For each sampled pond at each site, we calculated two groups of diversity metrics. The first group of metrics characterizes the faunal composition of each pond and thus estimates alpha diversity (hereafter we refer to these metrics as "alpha diversity metrics"), while the other group takes into account the rest of the sampled ponds of the site, calculated at pondscape scale, and thus estimates beta diversity (hereafter we refer to these as "beta diversity metrics"). The two groups of metrics were calculated for the entire community dataset and separately for the active and passive dispersers' datasets.

Alpha diversity metrics

We estimated alpha diversity using three metrics. We have calculated the rarefied species richness (S-rar) and the rarefied Shannon–Wiener diversity index (H-rar) considering the minimum abundance of individuals in a pond. The resulting rarefaction values are not the classical Shannon–Wiener index values but the exponential of the Shannon–Wiener index, which is equivalent to the effective number of species (ENS) and thus a more intuitive index than the classical calculation (Chao et al., 2014; Jost, 2006). Yet, we will refer to it here as Shannon–Wiener diversity. Finally, we calculated an index of taxonomic diversity based on the relatedness of the species such as taxonomic distinctness (TD), which uses abundance data. As we used unweighted branch lengths to calculate TD, steps between each taxonomic level in the tree are equal (Clarke & Warwick, 1998, 2001). The derived taxonomic tree used equal branch lengths and eight taxonomic levels (species, genus, subfamily, family, order, class, subphylum, and phylum), which were based on several identification keys (but mainly Tachet et al., 2000). This index is used here as a proxy of true phylogenetic diversity (Heino & Tolonen, 2017a).

Species richness rarefaction was performed using the “rarefy” function, and TD was calculated using the “taxondive” function of the “vegan” package (Oksanen et al., 2018). Shannon–Wiener diversity rarefaction was performed using the “estimateD” function of the “iNEXT” package (Hsieh et al., 2016).

Beta diversity metrics

We estimated three metrics of beta diversity. We calculated the “local contribution to beta diversity” (LCBD) (Legendre & De Cáceres, 2013) and the Bray–Curtis distance (BC-d), which are proxies of ecological uniqueness or assemblage singularity, the first using presence/absence data and the latter using abundance data. LCBD was calculated with the function “LCBD.comp” from “adespatial” package in R (Dray et al., 2018). BC-d was calculated from the community matrix as the mean value of the BC-d from one pond to the rest of the sampled ponds of the same pondscape. We also calculated phylogenetic beta diversity (PhBD) as the mean value of the pairwise dissimilarity of one pond with respect to the rest of the sampled ponds of the same pondscape. To calculate PhBD, we followed Hill et al. (2019). Because the true phylogenetic tree was unavailable for the macroinvertebrate taxa recorded in this study, taxonomic distance based on the path lengths in the taxonomic tree was used as a proxy for the true phylogenetic tree. We used the same procedure to create the

taxonomic tree as that for TD. So, first, the taxonomic distance between macroinvertebrate taxa was calculated using the “taxa2dist” function; posteriorly, a taxonomic tree was constructed using the function “hclust” and converting the resulting clustering tree into a taxonomic tree using “as.phylo” function in the “ape” package (Paradis et al., 2004). Next, pairwise distance matrices based on the Jaccard dissimilarity (using site-by-species matrices and the taxonomic tree) accounting for PhBD were calculated using the “phylo.beta.pair” function in the “betapart” package (Baselga et al., 2018).

Environmental variables

We considered ECELS (habitat condition), TRIx (trophic state), pond size, and ED (environmental “uniqueness”) as environmental variables. ECELS and pond size were already available from field data (see *Sampling and laboratory work*). TRIx index is based on the planktonic chlorophyll *a*, oxygen saturation, total nitrogen, and phosphorus. Numerically, the index is scaled from 0 to 10, covering a wide range of trophic conditions from oligotrophy (0) to eutrophy (10) (Vollenweider et al., 1998). We validated that all the sites showed similar variability in water characteristics (previously standardized separately for each site). To do so, a PERMDISP analysis was performed using the “betadisper” function from the “vegan” package (Oksanen et al., 2018). According to this analysis, the variability of water characteristics among the sampled ponds of the different sites was not significantly different ($F_{3,41} = 0.033$; $p = 0.990$). Finally, we used the environmental parameters included in Appendix S1: Table S2 (i.e., pond size, water characteristics, and the five components of ECELS index) to calculate for each site the mean Euclidean environmental distance (ED) between each pond and the rest of sampled ponds of the same site (i.e., a higher ED value denotes more environmental “uniqueness”).

Data analyses

We used linear models to look for the influence of centrality metrics and environmental variables on diversity metrics. Diversity metrics were the response variable. Linear models were used because the residuals and the Akaike information criterion (AIC) values indicated that the linear models fit the observed data better than more sophisticated models (as recommended in Zuur et al., 2007). Thus, for each alpha (S-rar, H-rar, and TD) and beta (LCBD, BC-d, and PhBD) diversity metric, we built a different model containing centrality metrics (degree, closeness,

and betweenness) and environmental variables (pond size, ED, TRIX, and ECELS) as explanatory variables. We used site identity (i.e., each pondscape analyzed) as a fixed factor and its interaction with the explanatory variables to identify the possible existence of differential responses linked to site-intrinsic differences. Thus, “main effects” indicate consistent results among sites, and interactions indicate site-dependent patterns. This procedure was repeated using the values of the centrality metrics obtained considering the two network approaches (percolation and community-contingent) and using the entire community dataset as well as the community dataset split into active and passive dispersers, separately. This resulted in six sets of models (i.e., two network approaches \times three community datasets) for each diversity metric (i.e., three alpha diversity metrics + three beta diversity metrics), that is, in total 36 sets of models (see Appendix S2). To identify relevant explanatory variables, we performed automated

model selection based on AIC for small sample sizes (AIC_c ; Barton, 2017). We then generated a subset of models with $\Delta AIC_c \leq 2$ using the “dredge” function. We obtained the explanatory variables’ weights in the subset models using “sw” function to have an idea of the importance of each variable (see Appendix S1: Tables S4–S9). The model selection procedure was performed with the “MuMIn” package (Barton, 2017).

RESULTS

Entire community

When considering the entire community, we obtained relatively high values of adjusted R^2 (ranging from 0.23 to 0.86). The fit of the models was quite similar when comparing both network approaches (Figure 4).

FIGURE 4 Plot showing the summary of the confidence set of regression models (community-contingent in red and percolation in blue) for alpha (left side) and beta (right side) diversity metrics using the entire community dataset. The numbers in parentheses correspond to the number of models included in the confidence set (i.e., model subset with $\Delta AIC_c \leq 2$ for each diversity metric; see *Materials and methods* for details). The size of the circle is proportional to the weight of the explanatory variable in the model subset. The intensity of the color corresponds to the percentage of models showing a positive trend (dark color), a negative trend (white), and a lack of trend (light color). The existence of trend has been established using the 95% CI of the slope estimate. The asterisk on the “Site” main effect indicates significant intrinsic differences among sites (e.g., higher values of a diversity metric in one site than in the others). The asterisk on “Interaction with site” indicates that the relationship observed between the diversity metric and the explanatory variable is site-dependent. Detailed information of each regression model is available in Appendix S2: Tables S1–S12. AIC_c , corrected Akaike information criterion; BC-d, Bray–Curtis distance; ED, environmental distance; H-rar, rarefied Shannon–Wiener diversity index; LCBD, local contribution to beta diversity; PhBD, phylogenetic beta diversity; S-rar, rarefied species richness; TD, taxonomic distinctness.

However, for alpha diversity metrics (i.e., S-rar, H-rar, and TD), the results obtained by the two approaches tested (i.e., community-contingent and percolation approaches) were quite different.

Thus, consistent centrality metrics effects were only detected when using the community-contingent approach. Considering this approach, we can see that degree and closeness had a positive effect on S-rar and H-rar and that betweenness had a strong negative effect only on S-rar. We can also notice that neither of the approaches identifies any consistent effect linked to pond size, TRIX, ED, or ECELS. Nevertheless, both approaches showed some site-dependent results, such as ED with S-rar and pond size with TD.

For the beta diversity metrics, community-contingent and percolation approaches showed more similar results than for alpha diversity metrics. Both approaches agree on the lesser influence of centrality metrics for beta diversity metrics (with the exception of closeness negative influence on PhBD, which was only detected when using the percolation approach). Indeed, all beta diversity metrics were positively related to environmental uniqueness (ED in Figure 4).

Active dispersers

For this group of organisms, the models obtained using the community-contingent approach had, on average, a slightly stronger fit than the ones obtained using the percolation approach (see adjusted R^2 values in Figure 5). Nevertheless, the patterns observed were quite similar between approaches.

The consistent effects for alpha diversity metrics were linked to both centrality metrics and environmental variables (Figure 5). Degree appeared as a main determinant, with a positive effect on all the sites for H-rar (Figure 5). Closeness also showed a negative influence for H-rar. The environmental variables were mainly important for TD, and to a lesser extent for S-rar and H-rar. While pond size showed a high positive effect, ED and ECELS had a high negative effect on TD. Pond size also had a positive effect on S-rar (only detected using the community-contingent approach). In the case of TRIX, it showed a minor negative effect on S-rar when using the percolation network approach. ED had a minor positive effect on H-rar (only in the community-contingent approach). Similar to the results for the entire community, some interaction terms were important, indicating that the relevance of some variables was site-dependent.

Overall, centrality metrics were less important than environmental ones for beta diversity metrics (Figure 5). Thus, only closeness showed some minor but consistent influence (having a negative main effect on PhBD, only

noticeable in some models that used the percolation approach). The rest of the centrality metrics showed a site-dependent influence, only noticeable when using the community-contingent approach (i.e., degree on LCB and betweenness on PhBD). Among the environmental variables, ED had a positive and consistent effect on PhBD and LCB, and whereas ECELS had a negative and consistent effect on BC-d and LCB, noticeable using both types of network approaches. Finally, pond size showed a positive and consistent effect on LCB values only for some of the models obtained using the percolation network.

Passive dispersers

For passive dispersers, the community-contingent approach showed better fit for alpha diversity metrics, while the percolation approach showed better fit for beta diversity metrics (Figure 6). The consistent effects for alpha diversity were linked to centrality metrics and environmental variables, similarly to what happened with active dispersers. However, and in contrast to our observations for active dispersers, for beta diversity metrics, consistent effects for centrality metrics were also obtained.

Regarding alpha diversity metrics, S-rar was the most influenced by the centrality metrics, which is highly and positively influenced by degree and closeness (Figure 6). Betweenness showed a minor negative effect on TD because it was only noticeable in some of the models obtained using the percolation network approach. When considering the environmental variables, ECELS showed a consistent positive effect on S-rar and H-rar. Pond size appeared to be important only for S-rar, with a main positive effect detected by both approaches.

For beta diversity metrics, both centrality metrics and environmental variables had similar importance. Degree had a main negative effect on the three beta diversity metrics, although this relationship was not always detected (Figure 6). Closeness also had a consistent negative effect but restricted to PhBD, and betweenness had a positive consistent effect, only detected using the percolation network approach, on both BC-d and LCB. The effect of environmental variables is mainly due to ED, which had a consistent positive effect on all beta diversity metrics. ECELS also had consistent negative effects on PhBD and LCB, but these effects were less strong than those due to ED.

DISCUSSION

The centrality gradient of each patch within the network is crucial for metacommunity assembly processes

FIGURE 5 Plot showing the summary of the confidence set of regression models (community-contingent in red and percolation in blue) for alpha (left side) and beta (right side) diversity metrics using active dispersers' dataset. The numbers in parentheses correspond to the number of models included in the confidence set (i.e., model subset with $\Delta AIC_c \leq 2$ for each diversity metric; see *Materials and methods* for details). The size of the circle is proportional to the weight of the explanatory variable in the model subset. The intensity of the color corresponds to the percentage of models showing a positive trend (dark color), negative (white), and lack of trend (light color). The existence of trend has been established using the 95% CI of the slope estimate. The asterisk on the "Site" main effect indicates significant intrinsic differences among sites (e.g., higher values of a diversity metric in one site than in the others). The asterisk on "Interaction with site" indicates that the relationship observed between the diversity metric and the explanatory variable is site-dependent. Detailed information of each regression model is available in Appendix S2: Tables S13–S24. AIC_c , corrected Akaike information criterion; BC-d, Bray–Curtis distance; ED, environmental distance; H-rar, rarefied Shannon–Wiener diversity index; LCBD, local contribution to beta diversity; PhBD, phylogenetic beta diversity; S-rar, rarefied species richness; TD, taxonomic distinctness.

(Borthagaray, Berazategui, et al., 2015; Economo & Keitt, 2008, 2010). Although we expected better overall fittings (i.e., higher R^2) for diversity patterns with the centrality metrics obtained using a community-contingent network approach than using a percolation one (H1 in Table 1), the differences were not as evident as initially expected and we did not find support for our hypothesis. However, when comparing both approaches, we never observed opposite trends for the diversity metrics tested. This highlights the fact that potential connectivity depends not only on spatial attributes of the landscape but also on the

dispersal ability of focal species (Calabrese & Fagan, 2004) and supports the idea of several scales of landscape perception among different taxa (Borthagaray, Berazategui, et al., 2015). Moreover, this fact also strengthens the power of the relationships indicated by our results. Nevertheless, it is important to remember that both network approaches present advantages and disadvantages. Percolation networks poorly represent the processes shaping local community structure because they disregard the specific scale at which local diversity is responding to landscape features (Borthagaray et al.,

FIGURE 6 Plot showing the summary of the confidence set of regression models (community-contingent in red and percolation in blue) for alpha (left side) and beta (right side) diversity metrics using passive dispersers' dataset. The numbers in parentheses correspond to the number of models included in the confidence set (model subset with $\Delta AIC_c \leq 2$ for each diversity metric; see [Materials and methods](#) for details). The size of the circle is proportional to the weight of the explanatory variable in the model subset. The intensity of the color corresponds to the percentage of models showing a positive (dark color), negative (white), and lack of trend (light color). The existence of trend has been established using the 95% CI of the slope estimate. The asterisk on the "Site" main effect indicates significant intrinsic differences among sites (e.g., higher values of a diversity metric in one site than in the others). The asterisk on "Interaction with site" indicates that the relationship observed between the diversity metric and the explanatory variable is site-dependent. Detailed information of each regression model is available in Appendix S2: Tables S25–S36. AIC_c , corrected Akaike information criterion; BC-d, Bray–Curtis distance; ED, environmental distance; H-rar, rarefied Shannon–Wiener diversity index; LCBD, local contribution to beta diversity; PhBD, phylogenetic beta diversity; S-rar, rarefied species richness; TD, taxonomic distinctness.

2023; Taylor et al., 2006), whereas the community-contingent approach allows for the construction of a connectivity network using a plausible distance at which metacommunity processes operate (Borthagaray, Berazategui, et al., 2015). Percolation networks, unlike community-contingent ones, can be constructed without using any other information than the geographical position of the patches, whereas for the creation of community-contingent networks, additional information from the patches such as species richness is needed. The use of contingent networks represents a step forward in quantifying further dimensions of community assembly that have a direct connection with diversity patterns and landscape structure. However, in our study, the community-contingent approach did not substantially increase the fit of the models explaining diversity

patterns and so did not turn out to be better than the ones obtained using a percolation network approach. On the contrary, employing an alpha diversity metric for the construction of our contingent networks may have introduced a potential bias in the obtained results. It is expected that there would be a heightened influence of centrality metrics on alpha diversity patterns in comparison with beta diversity patterns when utilizing the contingent approach. But this effect was not as evident as initially presumed as it only became noticeable when analyzing the entire community dataset. Notably, the relationships identified between centrality metrics and alpha diversity metrics for the active and passive dispersers' datasets were generally consistent with the percolation approach, which operates independently of any diversity metric. However, the consequences of basing

TABLE 1 Summary of the main results.

Hypothesis	Support	Observed pattern
H1: Percolation versus community-contingent network	No	In general, the models constructed using community-contingent network approach did not show better fit than the ones obtained using the percolation approach.
H2: Higher centrality	Partly	Centrality was usually positively related to alpha diversity and negatively to beta diversity, although we found few results where centrality negatively affected alpha diversity metrics.
H3: Centrality metrics	Partly	Degree, closeness, and betweenness relative importance for diversity metrics seem not to be related to the spatial scale but to the diversity metric and the organism group (dispersal mode related) analyzed.
H4: Environmental uniqueness	Partly	Environmental uniqueness showed a partial negative effect on alpha because it only affected the taxonomic distinctness of active dispersers, whereas a consistent positive effect on beta diversity metrics. The latest is true for passive and active dispersers, as well as for the entire community.
H5: Eutrophication	Partly	Overall, the expected negative effect of eutrophication on alpha diversity metrics was only noticeable on species richness of active dispersers; however, the lack of a clear effect (neither positive nor negative) on beta diversity might respond to counteracting processes as we explained.
H6: Pond size	Yes	Pond size, when relevant, showed a positive effect on alpha and also beta diversity metrics.
H7: Habitat degradation	No	The expected negative trend with habitat degradation and the diversity metrics at both scales was not supported because our results showed positive and negative trends depending not only on the diversity metric (alpha or beta) but also on the organism group (dispersal mode related).
H8: Active vs. passive dispersers	Partly	Our results support the expected trends of the relative importance of environmental vs. the centrality metrics for alpha and beta diversity in the case of active dispersers. However, for passive dispersers, an unexpected importance of centrality metrics on alpha diversity was observed.

the community-contingent network on maximizing the relationship with a beta diversity metric remain unexplored. Would such an approach yield a better fit for patterns at a larger scale? This critical inquiry remains unanswered, necessitating further studies to comprehensively assess the impact of utilizing different diversity variables in constructing community-contingent networks. Moreover, it is important to note that, in our case, constructing community-contingent instead of taxon-contingent networks may have blurred the landscape perception; because, by doing this, we assumed that all organisms within the same dispersal mode had the same landscape perception, which is not true. Indeed, active dispersers may show different landscape perceptions due to their known different dispersal abilities (Heino, 2013). Therefore, when possible, it would be advisable to use a more specific taxon-contingent approach to construct the spatial connectivity networks. However, and despite the abovementioned limitation, the community-contingent approach enables us to know which is the network that best represents the spatial processes that shape either the entire community or dispersal mode groups, as a first attempt to integrate a more

“functional” connectivity network that can be used in metacommunity studies. In any case, graph-based approaches have been proven to advance in quantifying the role of spatial and biological connectivity in a spatially explicit manner (Erős & Lowe, 2019).

The role of centrality

The importance of connectivity on alpha diversity has already been suggested by several authors, mainly in theoretical and experimental studies (Ai et al., 2013; Altermatt et al., 2011; Carrara et al., 2014; Economo & Keitt, 2010), but it has not been tested as much in observational studies (but see Ishiyama et al., 2014). Our work provides empirical evidence of this relationship in lentic temporary environments. Indeed, we found support for the importance of patch centrality enhancing alpha diversity and decreasing beta diversity (H2 in Table 1). Thus, we observed a positive effect of higher centrality on alpha diversity metrics. We found that ponds that occupy a central position in the whole network (closeness) and ponds with a higher number of connections (degree) have higher alpha diversity

when using the entire community dataset. Moreover, according to previous studies (Forbes & Chase, 2002; Jamoneau et al., 2018; Schmera et al., 2018), patches (ponds) with greater centrality, at both local scale (degree) and whole network scale (closeness), also had lower values of beta diversity, at least for one estimation of beta diversity and regardless of the dataset considered (entire, active, or passive dispersers communities). Indeed, we found a consistent and negative effect of centrality on PhBD, contrary to previous studies on pond macroinvertebrates that could not observe an effect of spatial variables on this metric (i.e., Hill et al., 2019). However, only when using the passive dispersers dataset, ponds acting as stepping stones (high betweenness) were also the ones with greater beta diversity. This result suggests that the differences among communities of passive dispersers rely on those ponds bridging two ponds otherwise unconnected and evidencing the strong dependency of these organisms on intermediate-scale connectivity (Suzuki & Economo, 2021).

Regarding H3, the results partly support our expectations (Table 1) that gave more relevance to closeness or betweenness when analyzing beta diversity patterns and a greater role of degree on alpha diversity. Instead, we observed that all centrality metrics were important for both alpha and beta diversity. Indeed, we observed an effect of centrality highlighting the movement of individuals throughout an entire network (closeness) on values of alpha diversity (Borthagaray, Berazategui, et al., 2015). This probably suggests the importance of the mass effects (i.e., local communities are dominated by regionally successful species that may not be locally adapted) among the more central communities (Brown et al., 2018; Henriques-Silva et al., 2019) because their assembly may be more dependent on the performance of species throughout the network than on local filters (Borthagaray et al., 2020; Mouquet & Loreau, 2003). Furthermore, betweenness also showed a negative but consistent effect on alpha diversity. This unexpected finding is difficult to explain because, until the moment, most of the studies working with betweenness centrality have evaluated the consequences of removing certain patches from a network in terms of habitat fragmentation, finding, for instance, that removing patches with high betweenness values resulted in a large loss of diversity (Thompson et al., 2017). However, a deeper analysis of the direct relationship between local diversity and betweenness centrality with empirical data is needed, especially in ponds with different topography, to confirm the negative relationship we obtained. These findings also reveal the importance of using different centrality metrics and demonstrate their complementarity in terms of emphasizing different aspects in relation to the

spatial scale (Economo & Keitt, 2010; Gouveia et al., 2021).

Effect of environmental characteristics on diversity metrics

Environmental variables such as pond size, environmental uniqueness, and habitat condition also had a relevant role in explaining alpha and beta diversity patterns. Supporting H4 (Table 1), at pondscape scale, environmental uniqueness showed a positive effect on beta diversity metrics, highlighting its effect on PhBD over the rest of the metrics when organisms' dispersal mode was considered. Therefore, this result reveals that habitats with environmental characteristics that stand out among the others present communities with more diverse lineages, which is, in turn, linked to dispersal-related traits (Saito et al., 2015). Moreover, at pond scale, we found a negative relationship between environmental uniqueness and TD for the active dispersers in agreement with previous studies (Heino et al., 2007; Heino & Tolonen, 2017b). In terms of the expected negative effects of eutrophication on alpha diversity and partially on beta diversity (e.g., Cook et al., 2018; Jiang et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021), we only observed a minor negative effect on S-rar for the active dispersers' dataset, which partly supports H5 (Table 1). It is worth mentioning that although there was a gradient in the trophic state among the studied ponds, overall they did not present any sign of eutrophication, which could explain the lack of strong relationships with the rest of the diversity metrics. However, when a strong nutrient input takes place in aquatic ecosystems, it can result in diversity loss and community simplification (Wang et al., 2021) or in stochastic response of community assemblages (Chase, 2010). Therefore, if both processes act simultaneously, then an absence of trend linked to beta diversity, as we have, is plausible.

Our results also showed the expected positive relationship between pond size and species richness (Oertli et al., 2002), supporting H6 (Table 1), but only for active and passive dispersers separately. Pond size particularly enhanced the sites' ecological uniqueness (i.e., the LCBD) when the active dispersers dataset was used, in agreement with previous studies (e.g., Yan et al., 2021). Pond size also had a positive and consistent effect on TD (used here as a proxy of true phylogenetic diversity) of active dispersers. The phylogenetic diversity–area relationship is little studied within aquatic ecosystems, so we had to move to terrestrial studies (Morlon et al., 2011) to find a similar result. The phylogenetic overdispersion found associated with larger patches could suggest that actively dispersing taxa are therefore not limited by their

capacity to disperse at these scales and can select larger habitats that, in turn, may provide greater habitat heterogeneity that can host more diverse phylogenies (Heino, 2000; Krauss et al., 2004; Rosenzweig, 1995).

Habitat degradation is expected to have a negative effect on both alpha and beta diversity metrics. Nevertheless, our results did not support this hypothesis because we found both positive and negative trends depending not only on the scale but also on the organism group (regarding dispersal mode) (H7 in Table 1). Thus, habitat degradation showed a consistent effect on alpha diversity for both dispersal modes, but with opposite effects (positive for passive dispersers and negative for active taxa). However, when looking at its effect on beta diversity, it was again consistent, but this time negative for both dispersal modes. Considering that all of the studied ponds presented an excellent habitat condition, we could deduce that, on the one hand, those with a lower condition (yet considered a good habitat condition because they have ECELS values of >70) are the ones that harbor the most different communities (i.e., negative trend in beta diversity metrics), and, on the other hand, those ponds with better habitat conditions present higher values of species richness and Shannon–Wiener diversity of passive dispersers. The latter is in accordance with previous findings in lotic ecosystems (e.g., Stoll et al., 2016; Terrado et al., 2016) and supports the idea on the enhancement of diversity associated with good habitat quality (Gascón et al., 2012).

Dispersal mode (active vs. passive dispersers)

We found partial support for our hypothesis that dispersal mode affects the relative importance of environmental characteristics and patch centrality for diversity. Thus, according to what we hypothesized, we observed that the environmental rather than the centrality metrics were more strongly explaining beta diversity of active dispersers (H8 in Table 1). Indeed, all the environmental variables tested except our proxy of eutrophication were important for this group. Hence, these findings support the idea that actively dispersing taxa have a better ability to track environmental variability (De Bie et al., 2012; Heino, 2013; Vanschoenwinkel et al., 2007). However, at pond scale, we were also able to detect some effect of centrality on alpha diversity of active dispersers, mainly seen in Shannon–Wiener index. Our results evidence the importance of having a high number of links to neighboring ponds (i.e., high degree centrality) for promoting taxonomic diversity of active dispersers, but at the same time, a reduction in Shannon–Wiener can be seen in

those ponds that were highly connected to the rest of the network (i.e., high closeness). The connectivity of a pond to the broader network facilitates the arrival of taxa from geographically isolated areas, particularly if they possess a sufficiently high dispersal ability. However, such taxa are expected to arrive in limited numbers due to their infrequent arrivals, thereby reducing evenness. This situation may account for the observed decline in local diversity among active dispersers in ponds with higher closeness. Conversely, in ponds well-connected to neighboring ones (high degree), local diversity tends to increase as arrivals are more likely to occur frequently, thus maintaining evenness values. This fact also evidences the importance of considering different connectivity metrics to have a clear picture of processes happening at different geographical scales (Borthagaray, Pinelli, et al., 2015). When focusing on passive dispersers, our expectations were not met (H8 in Table 1) because we found that centrality metrics together with environmental variables were more frequently related to their beta diversity. Specifically, betweenness gained some importance for passive dispersers, showing that ponds acting as stepping stones favor the dispersal of this group and hence improve their beta diversity. These findings also reflect the lower ability of the passive compared with the active dispersers to select suitable habitats and thus their greater dependence on spatial structures (Hill et al., 2017; Vanschoenwinkel et al., 2007). However, at pond scale, the different alpha diversity metrics of passive dispersers calculated were differently related to centrality metrics and/or environmental variables preventing us from accepting our initial hypothesis. Indeed, only species richness was driven by a combination of centrality metrics (mainly closeness, but also degree) and environmental variables. This seems to suggest that our passively dispersing taxa are enhanced not only by a high density of neighboring ponds but also when the pond is highly connected to the rest of the ponds configuring the network.

In conclusion, our results go a step further in incorporating and quantifying the relevance of spatial structure on metacommunity assembly processes and expand our knowledge of the relationships between site contributions to beta diversity and environmental and spatial properties, which are areas in need of further inquiry (Hill et al., 2017, 2019; Li et al., 2020; Specziár et al., 2018). Indeed, to our knowledge, this is one of the few empirical studies conducted on lentic environments that uses network centrality metrics representing the centrality gradient of communities and relates them with several diversity metrics at different scales. In this sense, we empirically demonstrate the importance of connectivity for enhancing alpha diversity and decreasing beta

diversity in pond networks, which are undirected networks, in contrast to river networks from which these results have been mainly reported (e.g., Pineda-Morante et al., 2022). Thus, as previous studies already highlighted, we also observed that the spatial scale is relevant for the centrality–diversity relationship (e.g., Borthagaray, Berazategui, et al., 2015; Economo & Keitt, 2010) and the relative importance of the environment and the space on alpha and beta diversity (Hill et al., 2017, 2019). The analyzed diversity metrics responded slightly differently to the environmental and spatial variables, suggesting distinct community assembly mechanisms acting at different scales (García-Girón et al., 2019). Therefore, our results help elucidate which factors affect diversity patterns, which is of general interest for the understanding and maintenance of global diversity. Hence, in light of our results, future research should examine multiple scales at diversity and dispersal ability levels, and the concomitant spatial and centrality gradients in order to globally consider the multiple facets shaping metacommunity assembly.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Irene Tornero conceived and designed the analysis, collected the data, contributed to data or analysis tools, performed the analysis, and wrote the paper. Stéphanie Gascón conceived and designed the analysis, collected the data, contributed to data or analysis tools, created some of the figures and Appendix S2, and reviewed the paper. David Cunillera-Montcusí contributed to data or analysis tools, helped with building the networks, and reviewed the paper. Jordi Sala collected the data, helped identify the samples, and reviewed the paper. Jordi Compte contributed to data or analysis tools and reviewed the paper. Xavier D. Quintana collected the data and reviewed the paper. Dani Boix conceived and designed the analysis, collected the data, contributed to data or analysis tools, and reviewed the paper. All the authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data (Tornero Pinilla, 2024) are available from CORA. RDR at <https://doi.org/10.34810/data1176>.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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